

Organize and Prioritize Appropriate Sustainable Tourism Development Strategies Case Study: Mazandaran Province

Meysam Ramyar

Faculty of Built Environment and Surveying, UTM, Johor, Malaysia

ABSTRACT: The present study aims to identify the encouraging and deterrent forces in tourism development, and appropriate strategies were organized and prioritized. In this way, the encouraging and deterrent forces are first identified and then prioritized according to the ANP method. In the second stage, using the model PIP, the most appropriate development strategies for sustainable tourism in the Mazandaran province was developed for the most important forces. Finally, for prioritization, systems establish a pairwise comparison between approaches formulated based on research sub-criteria. Besides, the research results showed that "creating jobs" and "increasing property prices" are the most important among the encouraging and deterrent forces. Among the strategies presented, strategy (A-1) with a coefficient of 0/0823 emphasizes optimal and purposeful use of increasing motivation travel among people to take advantage of tourist attractions and products to create employment and income for the province's people suggested as the best strategy.

KEYWORDS: Strategy, Sustainable Tourism, Mazandaran Province, PIP Model, Analysis Network Process (ANP).

INTRODUCTION

Today, the tourism industry has become an influential phenomenon in the global economy. Many countries view the industry as a significant source of income, employment, and private sector growth know the underlying development structure. It is of great importance; tourism development provides economic, social, cultural, political and legal aspects (Tribe, 2011). Nevertheless, multidimensional tourism industry and much activity with positive and negative consequences without planning and strategies unintended consequences and abnormal effects can be obtained from its development. This is a significant challenge for the specific views of tourism organizations themselves focused on reducing the negative impacts of the tourism industry. At the same time, its positive effects, including its contribution to the region's development, is increased (Peattie, 2016).

The main commodity of tourism is not like other industrial products. This industry commodities' unique feature are people, culture, traditions, customs, and living environment. At this mode of tourism, business activity increases the ability to sell this good without having constituent elements damage or eventually destroy these elements. If these activities lead to environmental and cultural erosion, the consumer of tourist goods suffers. This concern has led to a new debate entitled Sustainable Tourism Development (Hazbun, 2004).

In tourism, sustainable tourism is derived from the general concept of sustainable development, first in 1987 at the World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED) entitled "Our Common Future" was used, which combines the concepts of economic development and the formulation and prioritization of environmental protection strategies. Hence, the tourism industry's planning, guidance, and development is an essential resource to earn money and create jobs with social, cultural, and biological effects. But guiding this process is possible with scientific knowledge of the capabilities and bottlenecks in each region of the country. Mazandaran province, due to having privileged tourist areas, has many capabilities to attract tourists. In general, it can have a significant impact on the region's economy. However, evidence has shown the lack of prosperity in the tourism industry and the disappearance of tourism sites in the province. Primarily codified programs to address the issue of tourism development is not stable (Aryan, 2015). In this research, analyzing the tourism industry's situation in Iran, its functions and obstacles, and strategies to create a sustainable tourism industry has been studied in Iran. In this research, the industrial title with economic, social and cultural functions emphasizes developing tourism in Iran. Besides, the research discusses sustainable tourism and the challenges and barriers to achieving sustainable tourism difficult. The most challenges to achieving sustainable tourism in Iran include economic barriers, social, educational, and research lack of welfare, cultural and propaganda facilities.

Application of strategic analytical approach on internal and external factors and comparing these factors with each other, four types offensive, defensive, adaptive and contingent strategies were identified (Naji-Azimi & Rahim Nia, 2020). On the other hand, evaluation of internal and external factors shows that in the present conditions of among the methods mentioned, contingency

Organize and Prioritize Appropriate Sustainable Tourism Development Strategies Case Study: Mazandaran Province

strategies with facts, goals, and scale responding to more challenges and issues are more consistent through this strategy strength and consideration of threats (economic fields), Social, physical, environmental and natural infrastructure and management can be the goals of the case realize the idea and be relatively responsive to challenges (Ramyar & Halim, 2020).

Accordingly, the present study seeks to answer this fundamental question:

What are the forces hindering and encouraging the development of sustainable tourism in Mazandaran province?

And what strategies are more appropriate for the development of sustainable tourism in Mazandaran province?

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF RESEARCH

The Concept of Sustainable Tourism Development

There are different definitions of sustainable tourism development: endogenous development, environmental development, moderate and balanced development, comprehensive development, responsible and named notable tourism development. Endogenous development, mainly on internal resources which relies on environment-oriented development, puts its attention and emphasis on the environment. Development specific tourism is based on the idea that each region should be given different cultural, economic, and environmental factors - its tourism and tourists be consistent with culture (Sharpley, 2009). Responsible development also meets your expectations and meet the needs of the community. Balanced and comprehensive development to all existing factors society and the environment pay attention and combine all the factors to make an optimal choice achieve in development. In sustainable tourism, the effort is to meet the needs of present and future generations, between short-term benefits and environmental protection, maintaining cultural identity and promoting economic benefits balance both developed and developing societies; Sustainable tourism is a way to do the planning, know tourism policy and development, and in this way, the profits are optimally shared destination populations are distributed by governments, tourists and investors (Turker, 2009). Sustainable tourism development is the process of satisfying the needs of present and future generations of tourism producers and customers without destroying the resources that support life or the cultural identity and tourism systems (Negruşa et al., 2015). In general, from the point of view of the World Tourism Organization: »Sustainable tourism needs of tourists meets the present and the host communities, while also providing opportunities for the future expands and uses resources in a way that simultaneously with preservation of cultural values, ecological processes, biodiversity and support systems life, to meet the economic, social and aesthetic needs (Pan et al., 2018). According to this definition, sustainable tourism is a multidimensional concept with ecological dimensions, economic, social, cultural, and institutional. In this framework, the development of sustainable tourism includes:

- The environmental challenge in the form of resistance to the loss of natural and ecological resources.
- The economic challenges in increasing the income of the present society while generating income guarantee the future.
- The social challenge in the form of promoting social justice, security and equality.
- The cultural challenge in the form of protection and promotion of cultures and aesthetic values.
- The institutional challenge in the form of promoting the participation of local communities in strategic decision making.

In sustainable tourism development, the main goal is to provide rational methods in taking advantage of natural and human resources and prevent the unscientific use of these resources. Sustainable Development tourism has three aspects: 1) environmental protection, 2) conservation of resources and culture, and 3) respect for communities. Hence, sustainable tourism should implement a clear and codified policy to make a promising move to ensure the geographical aspect of spaces (Øian et al.,2018).

PIP Model

The rapid growth of technology, economic markets and social and political changes constantly pressure organizations and motivating forces, or the deterrent is challenging the organization. This is important for organizations on the path to recovery, moving towards the future, relying on past experiences. These experiences may be unrelated to the new problems that lie ahead. Still, if it adopts appropriate strategies based on the surrounding forces, organizations should have a forward-looking approach rather than a passive one. As mentioned, according to the PIP method, problems are first identified, analyzed and then the deterrent and motivating forces that cause issues potential or actual troubleshooting are determined (Wilensky, 2015). Finally, strategies for interest take on motivating forces and counter deterrents for programs improvements are identified. The performance improvement planning model process in table 1 summarized.

Table 1. PIP model process

Activities	Step
Determining performance indicators and prioritizing goals Predict future performance	Step 1

Organize and Prioritize Appropriate Sustainable Tourism Development Strategies Case Study: Mazandaran Province

Identify and analyze performance problems Determining deterrent and motivating forces Troubleshooting and categorizing problems Assess the relative strength of deterrent and motivating forces	Step 2
Develop a strategy for each deterrent or motivator Deep thinking to create new ideas Identify potential and actual possibilities Develop a performance improvement plan for the organization	Step 3

Analysis Network Process (ANP)

Analysis Network Process is a new theory that provides a hierarchical analysis process for addresses dependency development in feedback and uses the meta-matrix approach to this end. ANP method to solve problems that depend on options or the criteria is being established. It consists of three main steps: modelling and structure of the problem, forming a matrix of pairwise comparisons and precedence vectors, and presenting a supermatrix (Martin et al., 2013).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research is a descriptive survey in terms of data collection and order to purpose. To collect data and analyze information from studies, library, interview and questionnaire used. This study's statistical population includes experts and thinkers of government departments and organizations related to the tourism and hotel industry and owners of travel and recreation agencies in Mazandaran province. In this study, a non-probability and purposeful judgment sampling method was used to select the individuals. Therefore, due to the limited number of experts in the tourism industry in Mazandaran province and after a thorough review and identification of experts, 40 questionnaires were distributed by the researcher in person, and 30 questionnaires were collected and analyzed. The analysis method in this research includes four main stages: in the first stage, the purpose of the study and the criteria for achieving this goal have been determined. According to the research, the most crucial objective of the present study; selecting the appropriate strategy for developing sustainable tourism in the Mazandaran province. To achieve this goal, four criteria: economic, social-Cultural, environmental and institutional. Applying the above criteria is a tourist area to achieve sustainable development in tourism; it faces four economic, socio-cultural, ecological and institutional challenges. Therefore in the present study addresses, these challenges as criteria for achieving sustainable tourism were researched. In the second stage; After studying the background and research literature, a list of factors in the economic, socio-cultural, environmental and institutional fields that positively impact or negatively on sustainable tourism were identified. Then through an interview with experts and tourism experts of Mazandaran province, among the above factors, the factors that affect sustainable tourism in the province were selected as motivating forces and inhibitor in the development of sustainable tourism in Mazandaran, which plays the following role in the present study. In the third stage, based on the information obtained from previous stages of the questionnaire based on the network analysis process with a 9-point design, and distributed among tourism experts and experts in Mazandaran province. The priority criteria and sub-criteria of the research were determined in proportion to the purpose of the study. At the end of stage third, developing sustainable tourism in the province is one of the fundamental forces incentives and inhibitors. Finally, in the fourth stage; From the respondents, the importance of each of the proposed strategies was requested based on the following criteria research specify. By collecting and entering these comments into the above software, strategies were also prioritized.

RESEARCH FINDINGS

Step one: determining the purpose of the research and the criteria for achieving the goal. This research aims to formulate and select a strategy for developing sustainable tourism in the Mazandaran province. After reviewing the research literature, four indicators; economic, socio-cultural, environmental and institutional. Second stage: identifying the forces that encourage and hinder the development of sustainable tourism basis on research criteria. After reviewing the research literature and interviews with expert's tourism of Mazandaran province, influential motivating and deterrent forces in developing sustainable tourism in economic, socio-cultural, environmental and the institution were identified.

Table 2. Identification of forces hindering and encouraging the development of sustainable tourism in Mazandaran province

Deterrent forces	Encouraging forces	
1. Increase in property prices (1-N) 2. Increase in selling prices during the season tourism (2-N) 3. Having the opportunity cost(3-N) 4. Seasonality of job opportunities (4-N)	1. Job creation (1-P) 2. Monetization (2-P)	Economic (1-C)

Organize and Prioritize Appropriate Sustainable Tourism Development Strategies Case Study: Mazandaran Province

5. Damage to systems and cultural resources, including danger elimination of minority languages (5-N) 6. Increase of social violations (6-N)	3. Improving the level of social life (3-P) 4. Develop and maintain museums, music patterns, clothing and culture (4-P) 5. Promoting social justice, security and equality (5-P)	Social-cultural (2-C)
7. Pollution and destruction of natural and cultural resources and Water reserves and loss of landscapes (7-N) 8. Air pollution, noise and scenery (8-N)	6. Rehabilitation of existing buildings and historical sites (6-P) 7. environmental preservation (7-P)	Environmental (3-C)
9. Declining demand for foreign tourists (9-N)	8. Promoting the participation of local communities in decision-making strategy (8-P)	Institution (4-C)

As shown in Table 2, eight motivating force and nine deterrent forces have been identified in the province. Thus, in one summary and simple analysis, the vulnerability in Mazandaran province is a high need to review and provide appropriate policies to address deterrents and use the motivating forces.

Step 3: Prioritize criteria and sub-criteria for research and development Mazandaran Sustainable Tourism Strategies

At this stage, the collected information obtained from the questionnaires using soft decision super software was analyzed. In the ANP model, super matrix calculations are performed in three steps. First, the calculated weight values for all even comparisons are entered into a single matrix in the so-called weightless super matrix. In the next step, the weighted super matrix is calculated by multiplying the weightless super matrix by the corresponding values of the criteria comparison matrix. Then the matrix values are weighted standardized so that the sum of the importance of the matrix columns is equal to one. In the third and final step, the super limit matrix, in which the values of the matrix of the orthogons are similar, is calculated. Besides, using the super matrix, the final weights of the criteria, sub-criteria and research options with the research objective are determined. Therefore, in the present study, to obtain the absolute priority of the criteria, sub-criteria and research options over the research purpose, the research limit matrix is used. Tables 3 and 4 prioritize the criteria and sub-criteria of the research obtained.

Table 3. Priority of research criteria over the purpose of the research

Criteria	Ranking of prioritized values relative to the purpose of the research	Rank
1-C	0/16231	1
3-C	0/10103	2
2-C	0/04647	3
4-C	0/02351	4

As Table 3 shows, among the research criteria, criterion 1-C (Economic) with a coefficient of 0/16231, rank one and then 3-C criteria (environmental), (2-C) (Socio-cultural) and institutional 4-C criteria with coefficients of 0/10103, 0/04648 and 0/02351 got the ranks of 2 to 4.

Table 4. Priority of research criteria over research goal

Deterrent forces			Encouraging forces		
Sub-criterion	Prioritized values Towards the purpose of the research	Rank	Sub-criterion	Prioritized values Towards the purpose of the research	Rank
1-N	0/02985	1	1-P	0/03257	1
7-N	0/02560	2	2-P	0/02830	2
2-N	0/02214	3	7-P	0/02747	3

Organize and Prioritize Appropriate Sustainable Tourism Development Strategies Case Study: Mazandaran Province

5-N	0/01711	4	6-P	0/02001	4
8-N	0/01708	5	5-P	0/01843	5
9-N	0/01698	6	8-P	0/01387	6
3-N	0/01573	7	3-P	0/01376	7
4-N	0/01114	8	4-P	0/01225	8
6-N	0/01105	9			-

Table 4 shows the priority of the research criteria below the research goal. Between motivating forces; Sub-criterion 1-P (job creation) with the highest coefficient of 0/03257 has gained priority, and sub-criteria 2-P (revenue generation), 7-P (environmental protection), 6-P (Rehabilitation of existing buildings and historical sites) with coefficients 0/02830, 0/02747 and 0/02001 achieved priorities 2 to 4, respectively. Among the deterrent forces; sub-criterion 1-N (increase in property prices) with a coefficient of 0/02985, the highest priority and below the 7-N criteria (pollution and destruction of natural and cultural resources and water reserves and the disappearance of landscapes), 2-N (increasing sales prices over-tourism season) and 5-N (damage to systems and cultural resources including the risk of elimination minority languages) with coefficients of 0/02560, 0/02214 and 0/01711, respectively, ranks 2 to 4 got it.

Step 4: Develop and prioritize tourism development strategies stable of Mazandaran province

At this stage, using the information obtained from the first to third stages, appropriate strategies for the development of sustainable tourism in Mazandaran could be developed and prioritized. According to the model PIP for the most critical motivating and deterrent forces (forces ranked 1 to 4), appropriate strategies are developed, so at this stage to use forces encourage and avoid deterrents appropriate development strategies sustainable tourism of the province is presented as follows.

1. 1-A: Optimal and purposeful use of increasing motivation to travel among people in the direct exploitation of tourist attractions and products to create employment and income for People's Province (1-P, 2-P).

2. 2-A: Creating a fund to support and manage beautiful and attractive areas in the province and restore historical monuments and buildings (7-P, 6-P).

3. 3-A: Capacity and determining the optimal population density in different places in Mazandaran province to reduce the pressure and overcrowding to these places and attractions and prevent their destruction and destruction (7-N).

4. 4-A: Monitoring commodity and property prices by related organizations during season tourism to exploit its various parts for the general (public and tourists) and block the stock exchange (1-N, 2-N).

5. 5-A: Identify and take advantage of attractions, products, and other comparative advantages tourism of the province to attract tourists and increase the region's cultural potential (5-N).

Table 5 shows the priority of strategies over the research goal:

Table 5. Importance of sustainable tourism development strategies in Mazandaran province

Strategy	Values prioritized to the purpose of research
1-A	0/0823
2-A	0/0667
3-A	0/0592
4-A	0/0699
5-A	0/0552

As shown in Table 5, among the strategies presented, strategy 1-A with a value of 0/0823 has the highest priority, followed by strategies 0/0699 and 0/0667, 0/0592, 0/0552 values in 4-A, 3-A, 2-A, 5-A, respectively rated 2 to 5.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Multidimensional industrial tourism is a very complex activity that has positive consequences and negative. Without precise planning and strategies may have unintended consequences anomalous effects are obtained from its development. This industry and reducing its negative implications in Mazandaran province, the present study aims to identify encouraging and deterrent forces and formulate and select a sustainable tourism development strategy. In this regard, the integrated model of the PIP analysis network

Organize and Prioritize Appropriate Sustainable Tourism Development Strategies Case Study: Mazandaran Province

process (ANP) was used. To implement this model in achieving the expected results, there were four stages. The following figure summarizes these steps.

Figure 1. General scheme of research and combined model of PIP and ANP

As shown in figure 1, the primary purpose of the present study is to select the appropriate strategy for developing sustainable tourism in Mazandaran province. Based on achieving this goal, the method of the analysis network process is necessary to prioritize criteria and sub-criteria specified so that the criteria are sub-criteria and the following criteria affect research options. Therefore, to complete the above steps, the importance and priority of criteria and sub-criteria and finally, research strategies from the perspective of tourism experts were appointed. After data collection and analysis, the information was found to be among the criteria: 1-C (economic) and among the following criteria: Sub-criterion 1-P (job creation) among incentive forces and sub-criterion 1-N (increase property prices) among the deterrents were given the highest priority. According to the prioritization, the most crucial tourism development strategies stable were developed in Mazandaran province. Finally, between the strategies determined based on the following criteria, a pairwise comparison was established, and the 1-A strategy was selected as the best strategy.

Based on the chosen strategy; to increase employment and income generation within the province should encourage domestic and foreign travellers who are tourist attractions to visit the province to create the ground for the development of the province. To implement the strategy, inviting marketing experts, capabilities, capabilities, and attractions tourism projects of the province are identified. On the other hand, the target markets are determined and based on a comprehensive marketing plan. Other matters include the publication of a booklet, catalogues and brochures about the attractions of the province (in both Persian and English) and distribution also provided in passenger terminals and airports of major cities of the country to introduce the attractions of the province and publish it in the press and magazines reputable country can also be mentioned by preparing a program of tourist attractions in the province and broadcast it on the local network radio and television and hold regular annual festivals in the location of these attractions and participation in tourism fairs inside and outside the country to introduce the capabilities of Mazandaran tourism. By creating an internet site, these attractions are presented in detail, and the latest information related to tourism to be offered to those interested in Iran and the world.

According to statistics published by the statistics centre of Iran, Mazandaran province, with an unemployment rate annually 17/3 in 2017, was recognized as the most unemployed province. This rate in 2018 has increased to 19/2, which is the second province after Alborz province (unemployment rate 19/3) unemployed nationwide. The main problem of Mazandaran province has been

Organize and Prioritize Appropriate Sustainable Tourism Development Strategies Case Study: Mazandaran Province

evaluated, and solutions should be sought to solve it. This was a bad situation in the province. To solve this problem, all industries must provide employment opportunities for young people in the province. It is an industry that, if exploited properly, can solve the problems of unemployment in the province. Hence the strategy (1-A) emphasizes increasing employment in the province through the tourism capacities of the province, as the best approach has been proposed from the experts' point of view. With the results of the present study, we can refer to the results of the research of Mosammam et al. (2016) pointed out, in this study, the WT3 strategy of the WT subgroup with emphasis on encouraging people to travel to Mazandaran province and advertise tourist attractions in the goal of the market has been suggested as the best strategy. Based on Toutakhane (2018) research entitled sustainable tourism in Iran: Functions, Challenges and Solutions. In this study, paying attention to the education of residents and tourists, infrastructure and facilities required for development tourism are consistent with the present study.

The economic aspect of developing sustainable tourism and its positive and negative effects were considered and strategies to increase Niagara's competencies to support sustainable tourism, however in the present study to present sustainable tourism development strategies in Mazandaran, all dimensions of sustainable development (economic, socio-cultural, ecological and institutional) was placed. It proposed a participatory planning process that overlaps with the challenges and deterrents mentioned in this study (Jayawardena, 2008).

REFERENCE

- 1) Tribe, J. (2011). *The economics of recreation, leisure and tourism*. Oxford: Butterworth-Heinemann.
- 2) Peattie, K., Peattie, S., & Newcombe, R. (2016). Unintended consequences in demarketing antisocial behaviour: project Bernie. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 32(17-18), 1588-1618.
- 3) Hazbun, W. (2004). Globalisation, territorialisation and the political economy of tourism development in the Middle East. *Geopolitics*, 9(2), 310-341.
- 4) WCED, S. W. S. (1987). World commission on environment and development. *Our common future*, 17(1), 1-91.
- 5) ARYAN, G. (2015). Economic condition enhancement in Bam city by creating a new tourist area, according to Iranian regulations.
- 6) Naji-Azimi, Z., & Rahim Nia, F. (2020). Combination of SWOT Analysis, Analytic Hierarchy Process, and Monte Carlo Simulation to Identify the Strategic Positioning of Crisis Management at the Ferdowsi University of Mashhad, Iran. *Quarterly Scientific Journal of Rescue and Relief*, 12(2), 93-101.
- 7) Ramyar, M., & Halim, N. (2020). Tourist Expectation and Satisfaction towards Existing Infrastructure and Facilities in Golestan National Park, Iran.
- 8) Sharpley, R. (2009). *Tourism development and the environment: Beyond sustainability*. Earthscan.
- 9) Turker, D. (2009). Measuring corporate social responsibility: A scale development study. *Journal of business ethics*, 85(4), 411-427.
- 10) Negruşa, A. L., Toader, V., Sofică, A., Tutunea, M. F., & Rus, R. V. (2015). Exploring gamification techniques and applications for sustainable tourism. *Sustainability*, 7(8), 11160-11189.
- 11) Pan, S. Y., Gao, M., Kim, H., Shah, K. J., Pei, S. L., & Chiang, P. C. (2018). Advances and challenges in sustainable tourism toward a green economy. *Science of the Total Environment*, 635, 452-469.
- 12) , H., Fredman, P., Sandell, K., Sæþórsdóttir, A. D., Tyrväinen, L., & Jensen, F. S. (2018). Tourism Øian, nature and sustainability: A review of policy instruments in the Nordic countries.
- 13) Wilensky, H. L. (2015). *Organizational intelligence: Knowledge and policy in government and industry* (Vol. 19). Quid Pro Books.
- 14) Martin, M. K., Pfeffer, J., & Carley, K. M. (2013). Network text analysis of conceptual overlap in interviews, newspaper articles and keywords. *Social Network Analysis and Mining*, 3(4), 1165-1177.
- 15) Mosammam, H. M., Sarrafi, M., Nia, J. T., & Heidari, S. (2016). Typology of the ecotourism development approach and an evaluation from the sustainability view: The case of Mazandaran Province, Iran. *Tourism Management Perspectives*, 18, 168-178.
- 16) Toutakhane, A. M. (2019). Planning for strengthening the city's economic infrastructure emphasises sustainable tourism (case: Ardebil City).
- 17) Jayawardena, C., Patterson, D. J., Choi, C., & Brain, R. (2008). Sustainable tourism development in Niagara. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*.